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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18457048>**INFLUENCE OF SOCIO-CULTURAL ENVIRONMENT ON FORMATION OF IMAGE OF LEADER
IN FINE ART OF MEDIEVAL AZERBAIJAN****Karimova Sevil**

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Adiunkt

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**WPŁYW ŚRODOWISKA SPOŁECZNO-KULTUROWEGO NA KSZTAŁTOWANIE WIZERUNKU
WŁADCY W SZTUCE PLASTYCZNEJ ŚREDNIOWIECZNEGO AZERBEJDŻANU****Abstract.**

This study explores the evolution of the visual representation of leaders in Azerbaijani art, highlighting how these depictions reflect broader socio-political and cultural transformations. The research begins by examining the ancient and early medieval periods, where leader portrayals were heavily influenced by hierarchical structures and sacred traditions, symbolizing divine authority and protection. Over time, as local ethno-cultural characteristics began to play a more prominent role, the image of the ideal leader acquired more realistic features, incorporating elements from various artistic traditions, including Hellenistic and Turkic influences.

The analysis then shifts to the early and mature Middle Ages, focusing on the syncretism of artistic traditions during the feudal period, where visual representations of leaders became increasingly complex, influenced by diverse religious and cultural elements. This period saw the synthesis of Turkic visual culture with Mesopotamian and Sasanian artistic codes, resulting in unique artifacts that combined these influences.

Finally, the study examines the Safavid era, where the art of miniature painting reached its zenith. During this period, the portrayal of political leaders became more personalized, reflecting the Safavid state's ideology and the monarch's intellectual, military, and cultural roles.

Adnotacja.

Niniejsze badanie analizuje ewolucję wizualnych przedstawień władców w sztuce Azerbejdżanu, ukazując, w jaki sposób obrazy te odzwierciedlają szersze przemiany społeczno-polityczne i kulturowe. Analiza rozpoczyna się od okresu starożytnego oraz wczesnego średniowiecza, kiedy to wizerunki władców były silnie uwarunkowane strukturami hierarchicznymi oraz tradycjami sakralnymi, symbolizując boską władzę i opiekę. Z biegiem czasu, wraz ze wzrostem znaczenia lokalnych cech etnokulturowych, obraz idealnego władcy nabierał coraz bardziej realistycznych cech, integrując elementy różnych tradycji artystycznych, w tym wpływy hellenistyczne i tureckie.

Dalsza część opracowania koncentruje się na wczesnym i dojrzałym średniowieczu, ze szczególnym uwzględnieniem synkretyzmu tradycji artystycznych okresu feudalnego, kiedy wizualne przedstawienia władców stawały się coraz bardziej złożone pod wpływem różnorodnych elementów religijnych i kulturowych. Okres ten charakteryzuje się syntezą tureckiej kultury wizualnej z mezopotamskimi i sasanidzkimi kodami artystycznymi, co doprowadziło do powstania unikatowych dzieł łączących te wpływy.

W końcowej części artykułu omówiono epokę safawidzką, w której sztuka miniatury osiągnęła swój rozkwit. W tym czasie przedstawienia władców nabrały bardziej zindywidualizowanego charakteru, odzwierciedlając ideologię państwa safawidzkiego oraz intelektualne, militarne i kulturowe role monarchy.

Keywords: Azerbaijan art, leader imagery, iconography, portrait, miniature, artistic traditions**Słowa kluczowe:** sztuka Azerbejdżanu, wizerunek władcy, ikonografia, portret, miniatura, tradycje artystyczne**Introduction**

In the contemporary era of global social transformation, the cultural landscape is undergoing a profound visual shift. The increasing prevalence of visual images across all dimensions of social and individual life highlights this change. This visual orientation of culture serves as both a response to societal demands and a reflection of the unique characteristics of different cul-

tural and historical periods. The modern society, characterized by rapid development, necessitates succinct and powerful imagery that facilitates quick comprehension of vast information flows. Simultaneously, the creation of specific visual representations mirrors the social, political, and economic paradigms of the times (Merenik 2014, p. 161-162).

In Azerbaijani art, the historical evolution of the leader's image offers a compelling narrative of cultural

continuity and transformation. The artistic portrayal of leaders has long been a subject of fascination, intertwining elements of reverence, power, and historical context (Waner 2014, p. 8-10; Bacci and Studer-Karlen 2022). The depiction of leaders in art not only embodies the values and beliefs of a given era but also serves as a tool for reinforcing political and social ideologies. As such, a reevaluation of these images is both timely and necessary in understanding their significance in contemporary cultural and artistic discourse. Finally, as art history demonstrates, the concept of the image has the potential to evolve into an “idol image” (Aliyev and Daimi 2018).

The tradition of emphasizing the leader's image has deep roots in ancient cultures, where the leader was often perceived as a divine or semi-divine figure (Knauss 2006; Stala 2018). This sacred perception of leadership, with its associated attributes of protection, influence, and authority, reveals the multidimensional nature of leadership. The artistic representations from these periods, particularly in the context of Azerbaijani art, reflect the evolving concept of leadership and its visual depiction through various cultural and historical lenses. This study aims to explore the progression of these representations, analyzing how the image of the leader in Azerbaijani art has been shaped by and has influenced the socio-political and cultural developments over time.

Methodology

The study employs a multi-disciplinary approach to analyze the evolution of the leader's image in Azerbaijani art across different historical periods. The research methodology integrates art historical analysis, iconographic studies, and socio-cultural contextualization to explore how the depiction of leaders has both shaped and been shaped by the cultural, political, and religious landscapes of Azerbaijan. The study conducts a detailed visual analysis of various art forms, including ancient numismatics, early medieval sculptures, and Safavid miniatures. This analysis focuses on compositional techniques, stylistic elements, and symbolic attributes to understand how leaders are represented. The study compares Azerbaijani artistic representations with those from other regions (e.g., Byzantine, Sassanian, and Turkic traditions) to identify unique regional characteristics and cross-cultural influences.

The study examines the iconography of leadership, including the use of divine symbols, heroic attributes, and royal regalia, to uncover the deeper meanings behind these visual depictions. The research categorizes the visual representations of leaders based on recurring themes and motifs, such as the divine ruler, the warrior king, and the benevolent monarch, to trace the evolution of these types over time.

The research situates the artistic depictions within the broader socio-political and cultural contexts of their time, considering factors such as the influence of religion, the role of dynastic politics, and the impact of foreign invasions and cultural exchanges. The research investigates how the depiction of leaders reflects the continuity of cultural traditions and the adaptation to new political and social realities.

The study relies on primary sources such as historical coins, sculptures, and manuscripts, as well as artifacts housed in museums and private collections. The research incorporates secondary sources, including academic articles, books, and exhibition catalogs, to provide scholarly interpretations and contextual information.

The study is organized chronologically, covering key periods such as the Ancient Period, Early Middle Ages, and Safavid Era. Each period is analyzed for its distinctive contributions to the visual representation of leadership. The research traces the progression of leadership imagery, highlighting significant shifts and continuities across different historical epochs.

The study involves collaboration with historians, archaeologists, and art conservators to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the artifacts and their historical significance. The research includes technical studies, such as material analysis and conservation reports, to gain insights into the artistic techniques and preservation of the works under study.

By employing this comprehensive methodology, the study aims to provide a nuanced understanding of how the image of the leader in Azerbaijani art has evolved and what it reveals about the cultural and political dynamics of the region across different historical periods.

Initial Aspects

The tradition of emphasizing the image of the leader dates to the earliest layers of human culture, characterized during these periods by a relatively uniform understanding. The sacredness attributed to the leader, the perception of divine selection, and their capacity to protect, influence, and dictate the actions of others guiding their efforts towards specific objectives reveal the complex and multifaceted nature of leadership. This topic continues to be of significant interest to contemporary sociological and political sciences.

In the artistic representations of the Ancient Period, the hierarchical nature of leadership was strongly emphasized. The depiction of an ancient Eastern leader, such as a king, on a grand scale, had a profound impact. These figures were artistically canonized, portrayed with grandeur, and imbued with dynamic energy. Such portrayals were highly recognizable, evoking feelings of reverence and awe. The leader was thus established as an unassailable and traditional guarantor of the common good and security.

By the end of the first century B.C., the image of the ideal leader began to adopt more realistic features, reflecting local ethno-socio-cultural characteristics (Luciano and Giaccone 2020). This evolution also had a significant impact on the artistic style of the period.

In the early medieval art of Azerbaijan, particularly in the decorative arts, the depiction of the leader synthesized elements from the pre-Asian tradition and the Scythian "animal" style, with a distinct tendency toward form simplification and generalization.

Albanian and Atropathian numismatics, which contributed to the development of Azerbaijani coinage, along with toreutics, exhibited traits of the Hellenistic style, as observed in the findings from Khynysly and Gabala. By the first century B.C., alongside imported

coins, imitative models were minted in Albania, likely intended for the domestic market (Babayev 2002, p. 182-188). These locally minted coins displayed a simplified and highly schematized style, leading to the emergence of original local types (Bieber 1949).

The images of rulers minted on coins, initially those of Alexander the Great and later of the Diadochi on drachmas and tetradrachms, adhered to universal iconographic conventions of the Hellenistic era. These depictions affirmed the 'tsar cult' and the syncretism of the king's image with those of Zeus and Hercules, incorporating divine attributes. On the obverse, the ruler is often shown enthroned (as Zeus-Etaphorus), accompanied by an eagle and a scepter, and depicted in a seated posture. The reverse typically features the ruler's head in profile, often depicted as Hercules wearing the skin of the Nemean lion.

Hercules was venerated as the first mortal to receive "divine honor," and he was regarded as the quintessential model of a true ruler. Consequently, he became the progenitor and symbolic founder of numerous royal dynasties across both the East and the West. Another common motif is the depiction of the ruler as a horseman, symbolizing the amalgamation of various ethnocultural traditions, particularly those associated with the Thracian horseman.

The image of Alexander the Great was idealized and heroic, often representing him as an incarnation of Hercules, incorporating the iconography of his ancestor, Zeus-Ammon, characterized by an uncovered head

adorned with horns. Initially, this portrayal of Alexander was employed by the Diadochi to legitimize the continuity of their authority. However, over time, the image of Alexander was gradually supplanted by portraits of the Diadochi, although the general iconography remained consistent. This transition is also evident in the imitative coinage of ancient Azerbaijan, especially in regions such as Albania and Atropatene.

Early Middle Ages. Syncretism of Artistic Traditions

The Middle Ages in Azerbaijan were characterized by the emergence of a new social order that introduced a variety of political and socio-cultural elements, defining the structure of feudal relations. Connections with ancient European civilizations, once replaced by Eastern Byzantium, became increasingly restricted. Within the context of Caucasian art, the four-century-long conflict between the Sassanids and Byzantines, culminating in the dominance of the Arab Caliphate, significantly influenced the development of Turkic ethnocultural elements in the region (Mammadova 2021, p. 183-194; Gippert and Dum-Tragut 2023). The coexistence of multiple religions during this period created a unique and multipolar artistic environment, fundamentally distinct from the European "Dark Ages." Unlike regions where religious dogma predominated, medieval Azerbaijan saw a synthesis of various religious practices. Christianity flourished in neighboring Georgia, while ancient beliefs persisted in parts of the North Caucasus (Ghoshgarly 2012; Filas 2018).

Figure 1. Statue of Javanshir, king of Caucasian Albania, National Museum of History of Azerbaijan (original in Hermitage), found from Nakhchivan, 7th century (Ibrahimov 2019)

The emergence of Christianity in the South Caucasus began with the establishment of Apostolic Churches and later evolved through theological movements such as Nestorianism, Chalcedonianism, and Mono- and Dyophysitism (Dodds *et al.* 2008). These theological debates became intertwined with the political and economic conflicts of the time (Dudwick 1990; Shariyev 2022).

In this diverse context, the visual representation of political leaders was heavily influenced by the prevailing artistic trends of dominant cultures, while also incorporating elements of local tradition. The selective aniconism inherent in Turkic visual culture, derived from the Scythian-Cimmerian "animal style," was closely interwoven with the artistic codes of the Mesopotamian tradition, ultimately culminating in Sasanian art (Aphonina 2016). A notable example of this stylistic

synthesis is the bronze incense burner from the sixth-seventh centuries, identified in 1959 by Camille Trever as a mounted statue of the ruler of Caucasian Albania, Javanshir (642-681) (Ibrahimov 2019; Shafiyev 2022) (Figure 1). It should be noted that censers from antiquity were primarily used in religious practices for 'sacred inhalations,' which facilitated acts of prophecy within temples. This context also raises questions regarding the attribution made by Trever (1959).

The political and socio-cultural landscape during Javanshir's reign was marked by the coexistence of diverse religious beliefs, including Christian (Byzantine), Zoroastrian (Sassanian), Tengrist, Jewish (Khazar Khaganate), and eventually Islamic influences. These influences profoundly shaped the stylistic originality of the artifact. It is important to note that such incense burners in antiquity were primarily intended for religious practices and "sacred inhalations."

Standing at a height of 35.6 cm, the artifact is distinguished by its intricate details, which Camille Trever highlighted in her initial attribution. The influence of Sassanian plastic art, characterized by its grandiose style, is evident in the overall composition, imparting a weighty and grounded quality to the piece, particularly in the depiction of the crown and costume details. The pose of the horse, however, reflects a synthesis of two distinct artistic traditions: the Persian influence, which adheres to the measured rhythm of traditional royal frieze compositions, and the dynamic iconography of the horseman-leader, depicted here with a raised left hoof a motif characteristic of ancient Turkic art ("Thracian type," "Hunnic type").

The dynamism of the "animal style" is apparent in the full-face heraldic composition of the stand, which features lions and a capricorn at its center, as well as in the intricate graphic patterns adorning its sides. The artisan who crafted the incense burner adeptly merged various artistic elements prevalent at the time with the widespread Near Eastern motif of the Priest King. This is particularly evident in the "Horseman's" outstretched hands, which may have once held torches symbolizing divine Light and Salvation. "Capricorn, as a symbol associated with the Scythians and one of the representations of their chief deity Papey (Zeus-Tengri), is prominently featured in Scythian iconography from the Pazyryk period (Hasanov 2002). It is noteworthy that, beginning in the early Common Era, Capricorn became linked to the Scythian milieu within the European tradition. The emblem of Capricorn was notably adopted by the IV Scythian Legion of the Roman Republic and Empire (Legio IIII Scythica).

In Scythian pictorial tradition, the synthesized image of Capricorn with a fish tail appears in a dual aspect. In broader cultural and astrological symbolism, the signs of Capricorn and Pisces are interconnected, reflecting the dualistic tendencies of life, signifying both evolutionary and involutory possibilities. Capricorn is often seen as symbolizing the onset of disintegration, while Pisces represents the final moment, which inherently contains the seed of a new cycle. A similar iconographic motif (Capricorn, a dog surrounded by lions), with minor variations, reappears in

later periods of Azerbaijani art (Efendi and Efendi 2002, p. 67).

Engraved scenes, whose motifs symbolically depict the reign and attributes of power of Javanshir, suggest borrowings from existing traditions of ruler representation. One scene, depicting a battle between the king and a lion a motif characteristic of the Near East demonstrates the influence of regional artistic practices (Rzayev 1976, p. 112-118).

However, the depiction also reveals elements of the 'animal style' iconography. The animal figure displays distinctive characteristics: shortened legs, emphasized leg muscles through deepened lines, the head separated from the neck by a fold of fur indicated by a raised or grooved line, and the shoulder blades highlighted in relief.

These engraved images support the conclusion that pre-Islamic Azerbaijani art was developing a universal and idealized image of the ruler — one who is both a king and a protector, a bearer of faith, and an invincible warrior. Similar motifs are found on numerous architectural monuments of Caucasian Albania, particularly on the reliefs described by Geyushev (1984).

The Mature and Late Middle Ages. The Image of the Ruler in the Context of the Symbolism of the Miniature Tradition

The integration of Azerbaijan into the Islamic world and the establishment of various states on its territory during the post-Arab period laid the groundwork for a cultural renaissance known as the "epoch of Nizami," spanning the eleventh-twelfth centuries. During this time, Azerbaijan became an integral part of the Turkic-Islamic world. The emergence of a new civilizational paradigm during this period was a complex and multi-layered process, shaped by the imperial and cultural ambitions of the Seljuks and Mongols. This era saw a re-evaluation of the historical and cultural heritage of the region's people.

Nizami's genius transcended the conventional courtly literature of his time, as he crafted the image of an ideal king, removed from the immediate realities of his era. Characters such as Iskender (Alexander the Great, the hero of the eponymous poem), the sage and prophet Bahram Gur, and Khosrov served as spiritual archetypes. However, the subsequent historical and cultural developments called for more realistic portrayals.

By the late thirteenth century, amidst the flourishing of the Ilkhanid dynasty and the ongoing Renaissance, a direct visual engagement with ruling figures became a defining feature of early Azerbaijani miniature painting (Miniature art n.d.). The rulers depicted in Rashid al-Din's "Jami al-Tawarikh" ("Compendium of Chronicles"), a seminal work created in Tabriz at the beginning of the fourteenth century, were portrayed in various contexts on the battlefield, enthroned, and during feasts. These depictions would later influence the iconography of similar themes (Kerimov 1980).

The workshops of Rub'-i Rashidiyya attracted numerous artists, leading to the development of various stylistic trends in miniature painting. However, a commonality of style and subject matter emerged, creating recognizable iconographic themes in the depiction of

individual cycles and characters. The ancient painting traditions drawn from Buddhist, Confucian, Manichaean, Byzantine, Nestorian, and Syrian sources were significantly reinterpreted and integrated into Turkic art, both in temperament and in means of expression (Hasanzade 2014). The images of rulers, including those of Western origin, were characterized by dynamic poses (particularly in the three-quarter view of horsemen) and a sensitive treatment of angles. Distinctive attributes were used to make these figures recognizable, a hallmark of the visual language of Islamic art (Somhegyi 2023).

The art of miniature painting in medieval Azerbaijan, particularly in the regional schools with Tabriz as a leading center, reached its zenith during the Safavid period. The Shah's court took a special interest in manuscripts that depicted scenes of courtly life, such as hunting, feasting, *mejlis* (gatherings), conversations, as well as battle narratives and literary heritage. The portrayal of political leaders during this era was closely tied to these narrative compositions, with artists striving to convey the essence of Safavid state ideology within their works (Miniature painting, n.d.; Bell *et al.* 2013).

Figure 2. *Farruk bek Shah Tasmašp in the mountains, end of XVI*
(http://ids.si.edu/ids/deliveryService?id=FS-6558_02&max_w=600)

The artistic and aesthetic democratization of the image, highlighted by the distinctive attributes of the costume such as the Safavid turban adorned with an egretka creates a connection between specific members of the ruling family and legendary Eastern leaders, notably the heroes from Nizami's works. This integration places them within a unified pictorial framework. Notably, the Tabriz *Shahnameh* of Tahmasib (1530-1535) and the subsequent *Khamsa* (1539-1543) under Sultan Muhammad exemplify the vivid results of this approach.

By the mid-sixteenth century, the iconography of official portraits continued to evolve dynamically, with rulers depicted in various semantic and narrative contexts. Toward the end of the century, portraiture increasingly embraced personalization, influenced by extensive interactions with Western countries and exposure to their advancements in realism (Aliyev 2020, p. 31).

In the first half of the sixteenth century, the role of the Safavid dynasty in unifying Azerbaijan was deeply embedded in socio-political thought and public consciousness. This period witnessed an active development of ideological concepts concerning the nature of Shah's authority and their professional mission. The image of the ideal monarch adorned in exquisite royal attire and wearing the characteristic Taj-Haydari head-dress is often depicted slightly off-center within the composition. The Shah is portrayed seated on a throne, in a garden, or beneath the shade of a royal tent, surrounded by close confidants.

The figurative portrayal of the Shah embodies the qualities of an intellectual, commander, statesman, and philanthropist. In Safavid miniatures, this representation forms an independent visual, compositional, and narrative model, distinct from its Eastern counterparts. The figure of the Shah stands out against the dark backdrop of a garden or within richly detailed interiors, devoid of the courtly grandeur and hieratic ceremonial postures that characterized Ottoman miniatures of the same period (Kerimova 2020, p. 54-63) (Figure 2).

Several iconographic themes can be observed in miniature portraits from this period. These often feature young princes against scenic backdrops, such as flowering trees, holding a falcon and a book. Examples include "Portrait of Shahzade" (Tahmasib) by Sultan Muhammad from the 1540s and "Portrait of a Young Man, Sadig Bey Afshar" from the 1590s.

Another notable aspect is the neutral chamber settings observed in Mughal miniatures, where Tabriz masters invited to contribute to these works sometimes deviated from the traditional canons of the Safavid workshop (Allergorical symbols in Mughal painting 2020).

Farrukh-bek's miniature portraits are distinguished by their focus on individual features of the subjects. These works are explicitly labeled as portraits, such as "Amal-e Farrukh-bey, Shab-e Beiramoghlan"

("the work of Farrukh-bek, a portrait of Beiramoghlan") and "Shah Tahmasib in the Mountains."

Conclusion

In the context of contemporary global transformations, the visual orientation of culture reflects both societal demands and the evolving characteristics of various historical periods. This dynamic visual shift underscores the increasing role of imagery in conveying complex information and reflecting socio-political paradigms.

The evolution of leader imagery in Azerbaijani art provides a profound narrative of cultural continuity and transformation. The artistic portrayal of leaders has historically been a powerful means of conveying reverence, authority, and historical context. This study highlights how these portrayals not only embody the values and beliefs of their respective eras but also serve as instruments for reinforcing political and social ideologies.

The tradition of emphasizing the leader's image can be traced back to ancient cultures, where leaders were often depicted as divine or semi-divine figures. This sacred perception of leadership, with its attributes of protection and authority, has been a consistent theme throughout history. Azerbaijani art, particularly from the Ancient Period through the Middle Ages, reveals the complex and multifaceted nature of leadership through various cultural lenses.

From the grandiose representations of ancient Eastern leaders to the more realistic portrayals of the late Roman and early medieval periods, the depiction of leaders has evolved significantly. The integration of Hellenistic and local artistic traditions in coinage and other artifacts illustrates this evolution, reflecting the leader's role as both a symbolic and practical figure.

In the Middle Ages, particularly during the era of Nizami and the subsequent Safavid period, the depiction of rulers became increasingly sophisticated. The incorporation of diverse artistic influences, from Byzantine to Turkic, created a unique visual language that defined the portrayal of political leaders. The Safavid period saw the portrayal of rulers in ways that emphasized their intellectual and philanthropic qualities, distinct from the more ceremonious depictions of their Ottoman counterparts.

Overall, the artistic and aesthetic democratization of leader imagery, exemplified by the distinctive attributes of costumes and settings, establishes a visual dialogue between historical and legendary figures. The Tabriz Shahnameh of Tahmasib and the Khamsa under Sultan Muhammad are prime examples of how these visual representations integrate historical leaders with legendary heroes, creating a unified pictorial narrative. As the art of miniature portraiture continued to evolve, personalization and realism became more prominent, influenced by interactions with Western artistic traditions.

This study underscores the importance of reevaluating historical leader imagery to better understand its role in shaping contemporary cultural and artistic discourse. The transformation of these visual representations reflects broader socio-political changes and con-

tributes to a deeper understanding of the evolving nature of leadership and its artistic depiction throughout history.

References:

1. Aliyev, E. and Daimi, T., 2018. Iconoclasm and art. Available from: <https://syg.ma/@teymurdaimi/etibar-aliiev-i-tieimur-daimi-ikonoborchiestvo-i-iskusstvo> [Accessed 12 July 2025].
2. Aliyev, E., 2020. Iconography of Shah Ismail Khatai in European fine art. Baku: Europe.
3. Allegorical Symbols in Mughal Miniature Painting. 2020. Available from: <https://www.art-booklet.com/2020/11/19/allegoricalsymbols/> [Accessed 26 May 2025].
4. Aphonina, O., 2016. Methodological problems of the code and "double coding" analysis in the context of semiotics, structuralism and post-structuralism. National Academy of Managerial Staff of Culture and Arts Herald, 1, 60–65.
5. Babayev, I., 2002. Monetary circulation of Caucasian Albania in the Hellenistic era. Museum of the History of Azerbaijan, ANAS, 177–196.
6. Bacci, M., Studer-Karlen, M. and Vagnoni, M., 2022. Meanings and functions of the ruler's image in the Mediterranean world (11th–15th centuries). Brill. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358672789_Meanings_and_Functions_of_the_Royal_Portrait_in_the_Mediterranean_World_11th_-_15th_Centuries [Accessed 14 July 2025].
7. Bell, P., Schlecht, J. and Ommer, B., 2013. Nonverbal communication in medieval illustrations revisited by computer vision and art history. Visual Resources, 29 (1–2), 26–37.
8. Bieber, M., 1949. The portraits of Alexander the Great. Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society, 93 (5), 373–427.
9. Dodds, D.J., Menocal, M.R. and Balbale, A.K., 2008. The arts of intimacy: Christians, Jews, and Muslims in the making of Castilian culture. London: Yale University Press.
10. Dudwick, N., 1990. The case of the Caucasian Albanians: Ethnohistory and ethnic politics. Cahiers du Monde Russe, 31 (2–3), 377–383.
11. Efendi, R. and Efendi, T., 2002. Azerbaijani decorative art. Baku: BP, 67.
12. Filas, V., 2018. European tradition of the perception of the Northern Black Sea coast and its inhabitants in antiquity and the Middle Ages. Skhidnoievropejskyi Istorychnyi Visnyk–East European Historical Bulletin, 8, 8–17.
13. Geyushev, R., 1978. Christianity in Caucasian Albania. Tbilisi: Elm. Available from: <https://dzurdzuki.com/download/geyushev-r-hristianstvo-v-kavkazskoj-albanii-1978/> [Accessed 14 May 2025].
14. Goshgarly, G., 2012. Ancient Caucasian Albania in the system of international relations, 5th–1st centuries BC. Available from <https://udi.az/en/0073.html> (Accessed 14 May 2025).
15. Hasanov, Z., 2002. Royal Scythians. Ethnolinguistic identification of the "Royal Scythians and ancient Oghuz". New York: Lyberti Publishing House.

16. Hasanzade, J., 2014. *Mysterious tales of Tabriz*. IRS Publishing.
17. Ibrahimov, T., 2019. *Sculptural arts of Caucasian Albania*. Baku: Ecoprint.
18. Jost, G. and Dum-Tragut, J., eds., 2023. *Caucasian Albania*. Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
19. Kerimov, K., 1980. *Tabriz school of miniature*. Baku: Ishig.
20. Kerimova, S., 2020. *Azerbaijani-Italian relations: History and modernity*. Baku: Interpress.
21. Knauss, P., 2006. The challenge of making history with images: art and visual culture. *Artcultura—Revista de Historia Cultura e Arte*, 8 (12), 97–115.
22. Cheles, L. and Giaccone, A., 2020. *The political portrait: Leadership, image and power*. London & New York: Routledge.
23. Mammadova, F., 2021. *Caucasian Albania and Albanians*. Baku: Mutarjim Publishing-Polygraphic Centre.
24. Merenik, L., 2014. Epics, popular culture and politics in a modern work of art. *Etnoantropoloski Problemi—Issues in Ethnology and Anthropology*, 9 (1), 159–174.
25. Miniature art. Available from: <https://unesco.preslib.az/en/page/iuK2MwRPjJ> [Accessed 14 May 2025].
26. Miniature painting. Available from: <https://certindia.gov.in/miniature-painting/> [Accessed 14 May 2025].
27. Rzaev, N., 1976. *Art of Caucasian Albania: 4th century BC–7th century AD*. Baku: Elm.
28. Shafiyev, F., 2022. The mystery of Caucasian Albania. Available from: <https://www.obscurehistories.org/post/the-mystery-of-caucasian-albania> (Accessed 14 May 2025).
29. Somhegyi, Z., 2023. Cultural complexities and their environment: Investigations of code-switching in contemporary visual arts. *EIDOS—A Journal for Philosophy of Culture*, 7 (2), 27–35.
30. Stala, K., 2018. Role of ancient tradition in early-medieval art: Discussion on the European identity. *Teka Komisji Urbanistyki i Architektury*, 46, 711–721.
31. Trever, K., 1959. *Essays on the history and culture of Caucasian Albania 6th century BC–7th century AD*. Moscow & Leningrad: USSR Academy of Sciences.
32. Warner, N., 2014. Picturing power: The depiction of leadership in art. *Leadership and the Humanities*, 2(1), 4–26. <https://doi.org/10.4337/lath.2014.01.01>